

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D6.4

YEARLY PRESS-RELEASES, MEDIA KITS AND PROJECT FACT-SHEETS

Summary:

This deliverable is a compilation of the yearly press-releases, media kits and project fact-sheets.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

SUMEX aims to foster sustainable management in the extractive industry, with a focus on Europe. Over the project period, a number of outputs have been developed to contribute to this goal, e.g. the SUMEX Sustainability Framework and the digital toolkit, which consists of a knowledge repository and a massive open online course (MOOC). In order to disseminate the project outputs a broad audience, press releases, media kits and project fact-sheets on different topics were published regularly throughout the project.

Sustainability framework for the European extractive industry

PRESS RELEASE | BRUSSELS | OCTOBER 2021 – The SUMEX project is pleased to announce the release of a report describing the sustainability aspects that should be considered for the European extractive industry in the fields of carbon neutrality and circular economy.

SUMEX (Sustainable Management in EXtractive Industries) is a 36-month project funded by the European Commission that started on 1 November 2020. The project’s first aim was to **establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe**, with the involvement of stakeholders from civil society, academia, industry and government backgrounds from all across the EU.

SUMEX sees legal compliance with all applicable legislation as the baseline and as a minimum requirement for companies in the extractive sector. But even in the EU, legal compliance does by no means imply equal sustainable management of the sector. The project suggests one common standard to describe what responsible extraction should mean in the EU and suggests to use the IRMA (Initiative for Responsible Mining Assurance) Standard to describe the criteria that a responsible extractive operation should fulfil today. However, responsible management does not mean sustainable management. In order to meet this criterion, SUMEX recommends for the industry to transition, aligned with the European Green Deal, **from responsible extraction towards a future state of sustainable management**. This transition is described through the SUMEX sustainability aspects over a time period up to 2050, via the milestone of contributing towards achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2030.

In addition to describing sustainability aspects, the SUMEX Sustainability Framework also includes **evaluation and decision-making criteria** in order to assess a policy’s, project’s or operation’s sustainability.

“We see the Sustainability Framework presented in this report as a roadmap for the extractive industry in Europe to move from legal compliance and responsible extraction to sustainable extraction in 2050, aligned with the current European political debate. The sustainability aspects describe the topics and to some extent high level goals that the industry will need to consider most as part of the transformation required”, says Michael Tost, Montanuniversität Leoben, coordinator of the project.

For the SUMEX project internally, the sustainability framework will be used as a ‘funnel’ for **mapping good practices** from other projects and programmes such as Horizon 2020 or EIT RawMaterials and for analysing European policies targeting the extractive industry with regards to sustainability. These practices will then be presented in a **digital toolkit**, which will serve as the basis for establishing a **Community of Practise for engagement and peer learning** amongst extractive industry stakeholders across Europe.

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EU project SUMEX launches digital Knowledge Repository to help transform extractive industries' sustainability performance

PRESS RELEASE | BRUSSELS | SEPTEMBER 2022 – The SUMEX project is pleased to announce the release of a database that provides open access to good practise examples that could help transforming the extractive sector towards sustainability.

SUMEX (Sustainable Management in EXtractive Industries) is a 36-month project funded by the European Commission that started on 1 November 2020. The project aims to contribute to a sustainable mineral extraction within Europe. In this line, the [SUMEX Knowledge Repository](#) has been developed as a basis for capacity building and peer learning for actors of the extractive sector across Europe, including civil society, industry, academia and government.

Due to the climate change crisis, and as a response to other environmental challenges and the need to improve social performance, sustainability has become an increasingly important factor in the sector. To promote more sustainable mineral extraction in Europe, taking stock of knowledge and practice on sustainability topics is the key. The [SUMEX Knowledge Repository](#) is a collection of European sustainability practices which is easily and publicly navigable. Find information on the entire extractives' life cycle and along the five SUMEX focus areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessment, land use planning, health and safety, reporting and permitting processes. For this, our team assessed the potential of projects and programmes from [Horizon 2020](#), [EIT RawMaterials](#) or extractive companies to contribute to the sustainable development agenda in the European extractives sector. All actors in the extractive industry, from companies, permitting authorities to non-governmental organisations (NGOs) will be able to identify needed practices and embed them in their own. It will be especially relevant for industry representatives and members of public administrations wishing to understand and implement sustainability management at any stage of the extractive life cycle, from land-use planning to exploration to post-closure. This has the advantage that these practices have already been implemented somewhere so that their applicability and impacts are already known to a certain extent.

The [SUMEX Knowledge Repository](#) can be understood as a tool establishing an overview of sustainability practice and knowledge in the extractives and, therefore, informing decision-making on the strategic management as well as operational level. The project team works continuously on updating and extending it with new practices, with the vision that it becomes a useful tool for European extractive industry actors.

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Sustainable extraction in Europe – what does it entail?

PRESS RELEASE | BRUSSELS | OCTOBER 2023 – The SUMEX Consortium is pleased to announce the successful completion of the project and provides high level recommendations to European extractive industry players for sustainable mining and quarrying in Europe.

SUMEX (Sustainable Management in Extractive Industries) is a 36-month project funded by the European Commission that finishes on 31 October 2023. The project successfully **established an up-to-date sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe** and created a **database of already existing examples of sustainability practices** with the involvement of stakeholders from civil society, academia, industry and government from all across the EU.

Aligned with the European Green Deal's twin targets of an energy and digital transformation, in March this year the European Commission presented a draft Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA), which shall equip the EU with the necessary tools to ensure the EU's access to a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials. In parallel, the European Commission is also working on the implementation of the biodiversity strategy for 2030 to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems, which might seem contradictory to the CRMA. The SUMEX project results support the aims of the Green Deal for a just and sustainable economy and can support a successful implementation of both the CRMA and the biodiversity strategy for 2030.

First and foremost, the [SUMEX Sustainability Framework](#) created with extensive stakeholder consultation during the project duration and tailored to Europe is the most advanced framework at the moment and should be considered as a guide by the extractive industry, by policy makers at the EU and member state level, as well as civil society in order to enable mines and quarries to be aligned with societal expectations concerning the environmental and social consequences of mineral extraction.

With the advance of strategic projects under the CRMA and improved access to essential raw materials in coming years, this framework needs to be further advanced and kept updated by the European Commission, in order to enable land use and permitting authorities to make the right choices, i.e. how to measure and weigh different interests and trade-offs between benefits (often accrued remotely) and impacts (often accrued locally). This also needs to include a debate about responsible mineral consumption, i.e. sufficiency (how much is enough and what can be considered luxury?) and what will the minerals extracted being used for. It will also require significant capacity building for all land use and permitting authorities involved. For this, the SUMEX project created a [Knowledge Repository](#), that is freely available via the project website, and a [Massive Open Online Course \(MOOC\)](#), which is being handed over to the EIT RawMaterials to become part of their [RawMaterials Academy](#).

Land use conflicts between mineral extraction and, e.g. nature protection will continue to have high conflict potential in Europe. Mandatory instruments that promote a deeper understanding of the cumulative effect of land use changes would help. The lack of such instruments results in failure to

identify tipping points and safeguard the renewal capacity of natural environments and ecosystems exposed to multiple pressures, including extractive activities. This is the result of a policy misalignment between land use planning and extractives, e.g., not taking into consideration future extractive projects (requiring better knowledge from mineral exploration, as required in the CRMA) and associated land uses such as transport infrastructure, or not considering the implications of potential extractive activities on other land uses. The Strategic Environmental Assessment of land use plans could be an adequate instrument to tackle this, but policy gaps between land use planning and extraction should be addressed first.

All of the above will require more and accelerated technology development and a research-friendly policy environment in Europe. Only then will we be able to explore suitable, design and develop automated and safe extraction sites that operate zero-waste, have a minimal environmental footprint or even a biodiversity net-gain, are well integrated into a circular economy, and track materials across the value circle. Working towards such a transition of the European extractive industry is an opportunity for Europe to further advance its position in technologies, gain societal acceptance and attract also the younger generation to the industry.

Lastly, the over 370 good practice examples collected in the [SUMEX Knowledge Repository](#) should be used by all stakeholder groups to discover what is already possible regarding the sustainable management of extractive operations in Europe. They set the benchmark going forward.

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SETTING-UP A EUROPEAN SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK FOR THE EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRY

Media kit
October 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101003622

Sustainability framework for the European extractive industry

PRESS RELEASE | BRUSSELS | OCTOBER 2021 – The SUMEX project is pleased to announce the release of a report describing the sustainability aspects that should be considered for the European extractive industry in the fields of carbon neutrality and circular economy.

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SUMEX sees legal compliance with all applicable legislation as the baseline and as a minimum requirement for companies in the extractive sector. But even in the EU, legal compliance does by no means imply equal sustainable management of the sector. The project suggests one common standard to describe what responsible extraction should mean in the EU and suggests to use the IRMA (Initiative for Responsible Mining Assurance) Standard to describe the criteria that a responsible extractive operation should fulfil today. However, responsible management does not mean sustainable management. In order to meet this criterion, SUMEX recommends for the industry to transition, aligned with the European Green Deal, **from responsible extraction towards a future state of sustainable management**. This transition is described through the SUMEX sustainability aspects over a time period up to 2050, via the milestone of contributing towards achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2030.

In addition to describing sustainability aspects, the SUMEX Sustainability Framework also includes **evaluation and decision-making criteria** in order to assess a policy’s, project’s or operation’s sustainability.

“We see the Sustainability Framework presented in this report as a roadmap for the extractive industry in Europe to move from legal compliance and responsible extraction to sustainable extraction in 2050, aligned with the current European political debate. The sustainability aspects describe the topics and to some extent high level goals that the industry will need to consider most as part of the transformation required”, says Michael Tost, Montanuniversität Leoben, coordinator of the project.

For the SUMEX project internally, the sustainability framework will be used as a ‘funnel’ for **mapping good practices** from other projects and programmes such as Horizon 2020 or EIT RawMaterials and for analysing European policies targeting the extractive industry with regards to sustainability. These practices will then be presented in a **digital toolkit**, which will serve as the basis for establishing a **Community of Practise for engagement and peer learning** amongst extractive industry stakeholders across Europe.

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Links to further resources:

[Policy brief #1](#)

[SUMEX Sustainability Framework](#)

[Factsheet on the Sustainability Framework](#)

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Follow our activities:

www.sumexproject.eu

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DISCOVER THE SUMEX TOOLKIT AND ENGAGE IN THE EXTRACTIVE SECTOR'S SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITION!

KNOWLEDGE REPOSITORY

Browse an open-access data collection of European sustainability practices

MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSE

Join a free six-week course and learn how to apply sustainability in extractives

SUMEX MOOC

- Learn on your own time over six weeks
- Discuss with experts and peers the current state and challenges of the European extractive sector
- Learn about impact assessment, health and safety, land use planning, permitting, and reporting
- For young professionals or established experts
- Free access

KNOWLEDGE REPOSITORY

- Free to access
- More than 200 practices
- Relevance for sustainability transition
- Support tool for public policy and industry decision-makers
- High knowledge transfer and learning potential
- SUMEX verified and validated

Check out our resources and become part of a vibrant Community of Practice (CoP) driving sustainability in the extractive sector!

Take
me
there!

bit.ly/SUMEXMOOC

bit.ly/SUMEXRepository

www.sumexproject.eu

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SUMEX Sustainability Framework

Environmental sustainability

Social and societal responsibility

Transforming the economy (i.e. considering the Green Deal)

Baseline legal compliance

Responsible mining

2030 Achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

2050 Sustainable management of the extractive industry

Partner with host communities and society to deliver a shared vision of the future

Engage in continuous dialogue with stakeholders, create trusted grievance mechanisms and shared investigation and problem-solving processes

Safeguard human rights

Protect cultural heritage, i.e. regarding indigenous people and ensure free, prior and informed consent

Adhere to ethical corporate practices (no support of corruption, no bribes)

Diversity, inclusion & anti-discrimination (i.e. gender, young and old, indigenous people)

Share data and information transparently (incl. payments and revenues, environmental and social data)

Improving workers' well-being (zero harm, improved skills, fair compensation and terms of work, involvement)

Holistic management and continuous learning (systems thinking, company and site impacts, the ability to learn from mistakes, social/peer learning, reflexivity, continuous monitoring and reporting)

Planning beyond the mine life (clear time horizons, after mine life use, reclamation of land towards prior or societally relevant use, extraction as an enabler for succeeding activities/livelihoods)

Holistic risk management and emergency preparedness

Defining what „benefit sharing“ means (beyond taxes and jobs)

Accountability (i.e., life-cycle considerations and product labelling, various capitals, reporting)

Valuing all forms of capital, i.e. natural and social capital

Integrated, watershed-based water stewardship (incl. a focus on water efficiency and avoidance of freshwater use)

Efficient energy consumption, based on renewable energy

Carbon neutrality

Zero harmful air emissions

Arrangement of different land uses (spatial and temporal) and net positive impact on ecosystem services and biodiversity (incl. from indirect impacts)

Advanced waste management (considering secondary resources from traditional waste by-products, zero waste to landfill, no impact on surrounding environment)

Extractives' role in closing cycles, both biological and technological (beyond recycling, focus on reduction/dematerialisation, multiple use and redesign of products)

Understanding of the role and indicators for extractives in an inclusive Green Economy that exists within Planetary Boundaries (incl. innovation for technology "jumps", new business models, consumption patterns and "needs" considerations, linkages to other parts of the economy)

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SUMEX SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

The Horizon 2020 project SUMEX (Sustainable Management in Extractive industries) supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework for the extractive industry. The project started in November 2020 and in February 2021 an interim report, “D1.1 - European Sustainable Development Framework”, described the key principles of this framework and the process how the project team derived them.

In the subsequent report “D1.2 SD Criteria” SUMEX analyses the current debate regarding sustainability and the extractive industry in order to develop a sustainability framework suitable for the European extractive industry.

Within the SUMEX project, the sustainability framework will be used as criteria to identify and contextualise good practice examples within policies of the European Union (EU) and projects along SUMEX’s five focus areas. These will be synthesised and structured for an open access toolkit, which will be utilised for capacity building, learning and awareness raising actions in a SUMEX Community of Practise (CoP) in later stages of the project. For the European extractive industry, the SUMEX Sustainability Framework acts as a roadmap towards sustainability, as it brings together and maps current and future priorities of how the extractive sector can transform towards sustainability. In addition, it includes evaluative criteria that stakeholders can use to assess the sustainability of projects, extractive operations or mineral raw material products.

In the report D1.1 “European Sustainable Development Framework”, the team explored definitions and frameworks for sustainability and sustainable development and their implications for the extractive industry in Europe in order to develop initial, preliminary priorities and attributes for sustainability.

The project team then conducted in-depth interviews with extractive industry stakeholders to inform the final framework which will serve as a guide for the SUMEX project to identify good practice examples, concentrating on the five focus areas of SUMEX: permitting, environmental and social impact assessments, land use, health & safety and reporting.

Figure 1: Potential relationships between extraction and the UN SDGs as demonstrated by (a) Columbia Centre on Sustainable Investment (2016) and (b) AngloAmerican (2018).

SUMEX SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

In addition to the interviews, SUMEX also looked for evaluative criteria to be used for assessing and/or decision making in the sustainability context. As a result, the team found three evaluation schemes, and started to explore them further, to see which would best fit the later stages of the SUMEX project.

The SUMEX team concludes that a holistic and integrated view on sustainability (i.e. considering ecological boundaries, interdependencies among dimensions and looking into wider societal paradigms beyond the framing of an industry sector) is needed. Given that the scope of the project is the European extractive sector, SUMEX does not engage in any sourcing and supply chain or resource justice issues concerning non-European extraction.

SUMEX sees legal compliance with all applicable legislation as the baseline and as a minimum requirement for companies the extractive sector. But even in the EU, legal compliance does by no means imply equal sustainable management of the sector. SUMEX suggests one common standard describe what responsible extraction should mean in the EU: The team suggests use the IRMA (Initiative for Responsible Mining Assurance) Standard to describe the criteria that a responsible extractive operation should fulfil today. But once again, and as IRMA itself admits, responsible management does not mean sustainable management. In order to meet this criterion, SUMEX suggests for the industry to transition, aligned with the European Green Deal, from responsible extraction towards a future state of sustainable management. This is expressed through the SUMEX sustainability aspects, over a time period up to 2050, via the milestone of contributing towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2030.

In addition to describing sustainability aspects, the SUMEX Sustainability Framework (see *Figure 2*) also includes evaluation or decision-making criteria in order to assess a policy's, project's or operation's, etc. sustainability. In SUMEX, three very different schemes are assessed: i) Leverage Points, ii) The Seven Questions to Sustainability and iii) the Institution-Resource Regime.

They all serve different purposes and hence the project team decided to include all three them in the framework.

Figure 2: SUMEX Sustainability Framework. Please click [here](#) for a larger version of the image.

SUMEX SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

To sum it up, the SUMEX Sustainability Framework lays out a roadmap for the extractive industry in Europe to move from legal compliance and responsible extraction to sustainable extraction in 2050, aligned with i) the current scientific debate regarding sustainability except for the intra- and intergenerational justice perspective and ii) the current European political debate, i.e. regarding the SDGs, the Green Deal and the transition towards an inclusive, green and circular economy.

The sustainability aspects describe the topics and to some extent high level goals that the industry will need to consider most as part of the required transformation. The stakeholder interviews and desk research indicate the need for addressing extractive sector approaches from a systems perspective (leverage point analysis) in order to conquer root causes of the sustainability crisis, and making transparent and tackling tensions & trade-offs among different sustainability dimensions. The SUMEX Sustainability Framework tries to address these shortcomings - the three very different assessment schemes can be useful in describing effectiveness of policy measures and actions (Leverage Points, Institutional Resource Regime), but also the overall sustainability of an extractive project or operation (modified version of the Seven Questions to Sustainability).

For the SUMEX project internally, the initial testing of the sustainability framework showed that its components - aspects and two of the assessment schemes (Leverage Points, Institutional Resource Regime) – can be used as a ‘funnel’ for i) delineating and mapping good practices from other projects and programs, such as Horizon 2020 or EIT RawMaterials and ii) for analysing European policies targeting the extractive industry with regards to sustainability, as summarised in *Figure 3*. These practices will then be presented in a digital toolkit, which will serve as the basis for establishing a Community of Practice (CoP) for engagement and peer learning amongst extractive industry stakeholders across Europe.

Figure 3: Within SUMEX, the sustainability framework acts as a ‘funnel’ to analyse European projects and policies for good practices to be included in a digital toolkit to establish a Community of Practise.

DISCOVER THE SUMEX TOOLKIT AND ENGAGE IN THE EXTRACTIVE SECTOR'S SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITION!

Due to the climate change crisis, and as a response to other environmental challenges and the need to improve social performance, sustainability has become an increasingly important factor in the extractive sector. The **management and exchange of knowledge** are a key driver for this sustainability transition. Therefore, the SUMEX Toolkit provides the necessary knowledge and tools for **practitioners in companies and public administration** who are keen to engage in a sustainability transition in the extractive sector.

The SUMEX digital Toolkit comprises two components: A **knowledge repository of good practice** and a **Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)**.

A KNOWLEDGE REPOSITORY OF GOOD PRACTICE

What is in it for you?

- The SUMEX Knowledge Repository is an open-access data collection of European sustainability practices which is easily and publicly navigable.
- The SUMEX Repository establishes an overview of sustainability practices and knowledge in the extractives and, therefore, informs decision-making on the strategic management as well as operational level.
- Find information on the entire extractives' life cycle and along the five SUMEX focus areas: socio-economic and environmental impact assessment, land use planning, health and safety, reporting and permitting processes.

For whom is it most relevant?

- All actors in the extractive industry, from companies, permitting authorities to civil society organisations will be able to identify needed practices and embed them in their own.
- This will especially be relevant for industry representatives and members of public administrations wishing to understand and implement sustainability management at any stage of the extractive life cycle, from land-use planning to exploration to post-closure.

Take me there:

<https://bit.ly/SUMEXRepository>

MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSE

What is in it for you?

- Explore the importance of sustainability in the extractive industry and discover solutions along 5 key action areas are. The MOOC will allow you to:
 - Design, with other stakeholders, new sustainable management practices
 - Explain the environmental and societal impact of mineral extraction
 - Analyse environmental impact using tools such as the three pillars of sustainability
 - Discover sustainable management best practice in policy and industry
- Become part of a Community of Practice (CoP) around sustainability in the extractive sector and engage with and learn from like-minded professionals.

For whom is it most relevant?

- The SUMEX MOOC is designed for leaders, managers and stakeholders in the mineral extractive industry who want to learn about the challenges, solutions and new developments in sustainability.
- In particular, it allows public administrators and industry practitioners to understand and implement sustainability management at any stage of the mining life cycle, from exploration to post-closure.

Take me there:

<https://bit.ly/SUMEXMOOC>

www.sumexproject.eu

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FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS ON THE SUMEX TOOLKIT

How much does access to the Toolkit cost?

Access to the first part of the Toolkit, the repository, is free. It can be accessed via the SUMEX webpage at <https://repository.sumexproject.eu/>.

Are the courses accessible for free? If not, how much do they cost?

For the second part of the Toolkit, the MOOC, we are partnering with a professional digital learning provider, Future Learn. The basic access to the course is free and started in early November 2022. **You can still join and start your journey for sustainable management in the extractive industry!**

More information and registration: <https://bit.ly/SUMEXMOOC>

What is a MOOC?

A Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) is an online course which aims for unlimited participation and open access. These online short courses are a great option to top-up your knowledge or get an introduction to a topic in 4-24 learning hours. Many of the short courses are on-demand, so you don't need to wait for a start date to be available. Most courses are free to access and offer the option of upgrades if you would like to get long-term access to course materials and earn a digital certificate upon completion.

How can I engage with other professionals on sustainability topics?

To further discuss sustainability issues in the extractive industries, we invite you to join the **SUMEX Community of Practice (CoP) group on LinkedIn**.

A Community of Practice (CoP) is a group of actors that is sharing a particular practice and learns from each other. A CoP can exist as long as the members believe they have something to contribute to it, or gain from it.

What will be the expected impact of advancing the sustainability transition in the extractive sector?

The goal of SUMEX is to foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU. The SUMEX Sustainability Framework provides a roadmap for how this should look like.

More information: <https://bit.ly/3s6B3aV>

SUMEX Project background

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the EC that started on 01.11.2020. The project supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

To foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (*SU*stainable Management in *EX*tractive industries) will establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and will involve stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU.

This framework is then applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states and selected regions along five focus areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration-to find, or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader Community of Practise (CoP) and which forms the basis for capacity building. This CoP will consider relevant stakeholder groups, with a focus on permitting authorities, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars. In SUMEX, the experience from other projects builds a powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the whole raw materials value chain.

Challenge: No common understanding of sustainable management in extractive industries

SUMEX supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

Objectives of SUMEX

- Strengthen policy coordination and agenda setting along the mineral extraction value chain;
- Propose a uniform EU sustainable management in extractive industries context;
- Cluster with other projects to identify good practices and good practise principles;
- Identify good practises and principles for policy strategies and strategic approaches, coordination/integration and approaches and property rights regimes for different institutional systems;
- Build a toolkit with good practises, with a focus on access to land, permitting and policy coordination and integration;
- Identify stakeholder learning needs and requirements;
- Deploy an open access toolkit for capacity building across EU and with all stakeholders.

More info on <https://www.sumexproject.eu/>

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